

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON ARTISTIC DISCOURSE

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Abstract:

The paper analyses some characteristic features of artistic discourse as one of the types of discourse. Different points of view of linguists about artistic discourse, the functions of artistic text are discussed.

Key words: pragmalinguistics, sociolinguistics, discourse, artistic discourse, literary text, language, writer, reader, artistic integrity.

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Discourse refers to the use of language beyond single sentences. Discourse is an important study for the language because it allows individuals to express their ideas and thoughts effectively, understand and interpret the perspectives and opinions of others, and build relationships through effective communication.

In linguistics, discourse refers to a linguistic unit longer than a single sentence. The word discourse is derived from the Latin language *dis-* meaning "away" and the root word *currere* meaning "to run." Discourse, therefore, is translated as to "run away" and refers to the way conversations flow. To study discourse is analysing the use of spoken or written language in a social context. Discourse studies look at the form and function of language in conversation beyond its small grammatical pieces, such as phonemes and morphemes. Discourse is studied in sociolinguistics and pragmalinguistics.

One of the central theoretical questions that modern philological science is facing is the question of artistic discourse, i.e., how artistic enters into language, speech, and text. If in previous eras and in previous paradigms it was preferred to speak of such objects of literary theory as "artistic (poetic) language" and "artistic (poetic) speech", now it is discourse that became the object of the theory of language and literature. The concept of linguistic aesthetics presupposes an integral approach to language in its aesthetic function, to the aesthetics of verbal creativity. Linguistic esthetic theory at the present stage is based on such basic categories as artistic sign, artistic semiosis, artistic message, artistic communication. One of these categories is artistic discourse.

Romantic concepts of language are reflected in linguistic thoughts of A.A. Potebnya. In particular, on such a concept as "artistic integrity" (going back to Humboldt's idea of art as "integrity"), which played an important role in modern ideas about the languages of art. E.Kant's autonomy" of art affected almost all concepts of new art of the twentieth century, starting with aestheticism with its slogan "art for art's sake".

At the beginning of the XX century the focus of understanding the nature of art has radically shifted towards the study of artistic form as the most important element of an aesthetic object. Moreover, this understanding was consolidated not only among supporters of the "formal method". The concepts of art as formal, constructive and further actional mode of human activity comes to the first plan. At the same time, the conceptual attribute "artistic" does not lose its significance, but, on the contrary, increases its terminological valencies, thereby endowing its referent - the field of art - with new conceptual parameters and properties.

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Artistic discourse is one of the types of discourse and it is the expression of figurative meaning in an artistic work using language tools. From this point of view, artistic discourse is no different from ordinary conversational speech, but it performs, first of all, an aesthetic function.

Most often, artistic discourse is understood as fiction but it is far from sufficient. In addition to literature, artistry is also present in other forms of art with verbal component, for example, in a film, a theatre performance, a song. All these forms of creativity use artistic expressions, and, therefore, serve as varieties of artistic discourse as an aesthetic activity.

There are two main functions of a literary text: "creative function of manifestation of meaning" and "referential function of responsibility to meaning."

Creative, receptive and referential versions of the aesthetic discourse presuppose the corresponding competencies of the communicative event: "The specificity of aesthetic discourse (artistry) is the resultant of these three vector competencies and is nothing more than one of the fundamental communicative cultural strategies".

V.A.Maslova writes about artistic discourse in the aspect of linguistic and poetic consideration characterizing its distinctive features. Firstly, artistic discourse "creates a special, virtual reality, offers its version, a model of the world". Secondly, it is "a dynamic process of interaction between author and reader, on the one hand, and linguistic, social and cultural rules, on the other hand". And thirdly, artistic discourse "is created by social-individual reality, i.e. through concepts, categories and other meaning-generating speech processes". Perhaps such characteristics could be applied to any type of discourse in a culture, therefore, they are unlikely to be specific to artistic activity as such. On the other hand, the definition of artistic discourse is given here as a communicatively directed verbal work that has aesthetic value revealed in the process of its perception".

The important factor is aesthetic value of artistic discourse, however, it is revealed, in our opinion, not only in the process of perceiving a work of art (in this case, it is enough for the interpreter to accept any statement as aesthetic without context), but also taking into account the entire communicative situations of production, transmission and reception of aesthetic messages.

So, the artistic discourse is one of the most complex concepts in discourse theory. Each linguist interprets it in his own way, taking into account certain aspects of its nature. Artistic discourse is embodiment of a verbal message that conveys subject-logical, aesthetic, figurative, emotional and evaluative information, combined in the ideological and artistic content of the text into a single whole.

Any literary text admits plurality of its interpretations, which is caused by uniqueness of the literary work as a psycho-aesthetic phenomenon. The literary work is created by the author, in which he expresses author's individual ideas about the world, the knowledge of reality/events by means of certain language means, at the same time the author provides information for the potential reader.

Summarizing all interpretations with respect to the considered concepts, we can cite a definition: literary text – is a multifaceted, metaphorical reflection of reality, it is communication with a reader at the level of presuppositions, propositions, subtext, intertext, etc. It is characterized by a pragmatic focus, which is closely connected with the aesthetic function of the impact on the reader.

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